

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B295
Date: 19 June 2007
Take Off 11:13:11
Landing: 15:56:26
Flight Time 4h 43m 15s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Nouakchott - Niamey

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	CCM2 / Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	FAAM Ops	Steve Ball	FAAM
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office

Flight Track:

B295 Track 19-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B295
 Date: 19 Jun 2007
 Project: GERBIL
 Location: Niamey to Nouakchott

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
103209		INU	-.02 kft	098	to nav
103219		GIN	-.02 kft	098	power on
110437		taxy	-.01 kft	098	
110927		pirouette	0.00 kft	039	
110943		heimann	0.00 kft	011	open
111311		T/O	-.04 kft	219	Nouakchott
111318	113949	Profile 1	0.07 - 25.0 kft	224	
111356		heimann	0.52 kft	225	cal 11
113328		psap	20.0 kft	096	flow off
113447		!	21.2 kft	095	cloud layer
113645		psap	22.8 kft	094	flow on
113949	120150	Run 1.1	25.0 kft	094	
115159		Sonde 1	25.0 kft	077	
115543		bbr	25.0 kft	090	retract
115642		JW	25.0 kft	092	zero
120151	121544	Profile 2	25.0 - 15.0 kft	092	
120303		bbr	24.2 kft	091	extend
121544	123550	Run 2.1	15.0 kft	093	
121606		bbr	15.0 kft	093	retract
121802		heimann	15.0 kft	092	cal13
123551	124752	Profile 3	15.0 - 25.0 kft	091	
123802		bbr	16.6 kft	091	extend
123840		Video	17.1 kft	091	#1 ffc, #2 dfc finish
123904		Video	17.5 kft	092	#3 ffc, #4 dfc start
124753	135813	Run 3.1	25.0 kft	093	
124808		Sonde2	25.0 kft	093	
124818		bbr	25.0 kft	093	retract
125059		heimann	25.0 kft	093	cal14
132928		Sonde 3	25.0 kft	104	
135813	142349	Profile 4	25.0 - 2.9 kft	111	
141017		Video	14.7 kft	111	#3 ffc, #4 dfc end
141048		Video	14.2 kft	111	#5 ffc, #6 dfc start
141651		bbr	8.9 kft	112	extend
142350	144510	Run 4.1	2.9 - 2.2 kft	123	
142406		bbr	2.8 kft	125	retract
142431		!	2.9 kft	124	1000ft soft terrain following
142821		!	2.8 kft	125	slow descent starts
143056		!	2.1 kft	126	descent stops; run 4.1 resumes
144702	145208	Run 4.2	2.1 - 2.2 kft	306	
145219	145329	Orbit 1	2.2 - 2.1 kft	286	285M
145404	145516	Orbit 2	2.2 - 2.1 kft	238	240M
145603	145714	Orbit 3	2.2 - 2.1 kft	195	180M
145742	145844	Orbit 4	2.2 - 2.1 kft	151	135M
150017	150655	Profile 5	2.1 - 7.5 kft	320	
150313		bbr	5.2 kft	318	extend
150352		P5	6.0 kft	317	interrupt
150534		P5	6.0 kft	118	resumed
150655	151658	Run 5.1	7.5 kft	109	
150712		bbr	7.5 kft	109	retract
151659	152104	Profile 6	7.5 - 12.0 kft	115	
151717		bbr	7.8 kft	116	extend
152104	153104	Run 6.1	12.0 kft	115	
152119		bbr	12.0 kft	115	retract
153104	153619	Profile 7	12.0 - 17.9 kft	128	
153619	155626	Profile 8	17.9 - 0.82 kft	126	Niamey
155626		Land	0.85 kft	267	timed as end profile
155803		pirouette	0.85 kft	268	start
155954		!	0.85 kft	268	end

B295 Track 19-JUN-07

Pilot: Alan Roberts

NavData Cycle 2007-6 Expires: Wednesday, 04 July 2007.

Scale: 1:16756880 (1 inch = 229.82 naut mi). Printed on 19 Jun 2007

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.2.0.2

FAAM Sortie Brief

Gerbils: Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget Intercomparison of Longwave and Shortwave radiation.

Flight No: B295

Date: 19th June 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ and remote sensing measurements of Saharan dust and the associated effect on solar and terrestrial radiation.

Location:

Over land areas between Nouakchott (Mauritania) and Niamey (Niger).

Points:

Alpha : SUGGESTED point at 18°N, 5°W.

Weather:

High loadings of dust aerosols. Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

TERRA: MISR overpass at Nouakchott at 11:44Z

AQUA: MODIS overpass at Niamey at 13:10Z.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/wet-nephelometer combination

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS/SHIMS

ARIES

Flight pattern:

1. If clear from cloud, perform a 'pirouette' manoeuvre taking ~3minutes for a 360 turn.
2. Take off from Nouakchott at 11:00Z.
3. Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/minute towards the east until FL200-FL240 (25mins, T=25mins).
4. Perform a SLR (science speed not necessary) at this altitude towards Niamey (e.g. 60mins, T=85mins).
5. At dusty point Alpha, perform a profile descent down to MPA (20mins, T=105mins).
6. Perform a SLR at MPA (may be soft-ride) for 15 minutes duration (35mins, T=140mins).
7. Orbits at maximum angle of bank (10mins, T=150mins).
8. Perform a stacked profile ascent to FL 240 with SLRs of 10 minute duration at three different levels determined by the mission scientist towards Niamey (50 mins, T=200mins).
9. Perform a SLR (science speed not necessary) at this altitude towards Niamey (85mins, T=285mins).
10. Land Niamey.
11. Perform a pirouette manoeuvre if skies are cloud free.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B295

Date: 19th June 2007

Sortie Objectives: To investigate the in-situ and radiative effects of dust storms in conjunction with the GERB/SEVIRI satellite instruments.

Operating area: Land areas between Nouakchott and Niamey, along constant line of latitude 18N, before heading SE to Niamey.

Weather: Two significant areas of dust sampled via remote sensing and in-situ sampling.

Flight Patterns: A pirouette manoeuvre was performed at Nouakchott before take off. A profile ascent was performed from the surface to FL250. Dust was encountered from FL50 up to FL220, where it was capped by some altostratus. A SLR was then performed in the direction of Niamey. By 1150Z, the As had cleared and a sonde was dropped into the dust layer which was visually quite thick. A profile descent into the top of the dust layer was performed to FL150 where a 20minute SLR was performed and a filter exposed. Nephelometer scattering was at around $70 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ to $200 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$. A profile ascent was then performed back above the dust layer, and a second dropsonde was launched at 12:47 into the dust layer. The run continued to the east. ARIES/SWS/SHIMS data should be analysed from this run. At 13:25 a very high lower BBR flux (450Wm^{-2}) was noted which apparently appeared to be related to the highly reflectant surface rather than to increased concentrations of dust. A third dropsonde was launched. There was no significant cloud below until around 13:37. We then passed a large cloud region and moved free from cloud at around 13:53. A profile descent was then performed to 1000ft AGL, with very heavy dust loadings. The Nephelometer reached $250 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ on at the lowest levels. A SLR was then performed at ~1000ft AGL (approx FL20), followed by a reciprocal turn and a SLR. ARIES and SWS were looking both upwards and downwards during this period. A series of orbits were then performed at 1000ft AGL, where the solar zenith angle was 42degrees. A profile climb was then performed to FL75, breaking the profile to get us back heading towards Niamey at FL120 within the dust layer. A very little cirrus was detected ahead and to the RHS, but unlikely to affect the BBR measurements. A profile descent was then performed from FL180 into Niamey – the AOD was estimated as 1.4. This was in good agreement with the Banizoumbou data from the next day (allowing for advection (ish!!!)).

Summary: A very successful flight with a good mix of in-situ and remote sensing measurements. The data from the second dust storm penetrated will make a particularly good case study.

Problems:

PCASP did not work, although the second PCASP did.
BBRs are interfered with by HF communications.

18z_180607 AOD T+24

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 12Z on 18/ 6/2007

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.295** Date 19th June 07 Name JIM HAYWOOD Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					GERBIL flight
					Nauakchott → Niamey
					Nauakchott: Surface VIS good.
					No cloud, but upper dust visible.
					T = 25°C, T _d = 18°C.
11:07:00					Begin pirouette.
					No Ci overhead, but quite a bit of dust.
11:09:30					End pirouette.
					Start
	PI				Start profile ascent.
					Dusty, particularly inland.
					2 photos taken showing land surface & clear slot - climbing into dust at FL50.
11:33:43					Penetrate thin As ~ FL200
11:35:44					Top at FL218 clear from As.
					Some Ci showing above.
					8/8 Sc below
11:39:49	End PI Start R1				End Profile / Start Run
					Sc ends and then looks like a dust patch on the back edge
11:50:		FL250			Yes!!! ↑ This is true.
					A little Ci above.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.295** Date 19th June 07 Name Tim Hayward Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:51:59					Sonde #1.
11:55:20					BBRs now working - covered until this
					End R1.1 / St P2.
					Descend into the dust layer.
12:15:44	<u>End P2</u> <u>St R2</u>	FL150			Nice scattering $\sim 180 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
					@ FL150, top at FL165.
					Some variability in the scattering, perhaps a wave top? Aircraft.
					Still a little Ci around.
12:26:10					Point Kanad
12:28					<u>NOTE</u> BBRs are interfered with by HF comms!!!
12:35:51	<u>End R2</u> <u>St P3</u>				
12:46:53	<u>End P3</u> <u>St R3</u>	FL			Big convective cell to RTHS.
12:47:08					Launch Sonde #2.
					Sonde dropped into dust.
					A few patches of Cu below.
					A little v. thin Ci above.
13:05					Some Cu/Sc below - looks to be at the top of the dust layer.
13:20					Free from cloud
13:25					Appears to be a very bright surface below

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....**295**..... Date **19th June 07** Name **Jim Haywood** Page **3** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					(cont) Observers can see the surface, but lower BBRs $\sim 450 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$.
13:29:28					Sonde #3. Launched - cloud to south. No cloud below until 13:37.
13:43					Cloud / big dust interface $\rightarrow$ dust only ahead of us.
13:53					Very good conditions — no cloud above or below. Obs suggest diff H HF radio transmission worst on red lower BBR. Evidenced $\rightarrow$ 13:48 $\rightarrow$ 13:51. Profile descent into dust layer. Bumpy.
	End R3 St P4	FL220			
14:23:48	End P St	1000ft HL			Surface visible at 10,000ft $\sim 1000 \text{ ft AGL (FL27)}$

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.295**.....

 Date 14th June 07...

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:26					Heimann Ts = 50C.
14:28:00					Ease down by 800ft.
14:30 -		FL20 AGL ~1000ft	125		FL20, 1000ft. C = cal Z = Zenith N = nadir
14:45:10	End Rpt 1	FL20 ~1000ft			Turn onto reciprocal heading
	St Rpt 2	FL20 ~1000ft			
	End Rpt 2	FL20 ~1000ft	285		Orbit at 1000ft, 50° bank
	End 01	FL20 ~1000ft			01 angle.
	St 02		240		02 SZA = 42°.
	End 02				
	St 03		180		V. dusty → no cloud.
	End 03				
	St 04				
	End 04				
	St P5	FL20 ↑			Climb to FL75
	Int P5	FL60			Int at FL60
					Reciprocal turn
	Restart P5	FL60 ↑	111		Recommence P5
	End P5	FL75			Start Retn.
	St R				All free from cloud.
	End P5	FL75 ↑			Neph FL75 ~ 200 × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
	St P6				Dusty.
	End P6				
	St P6				

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B295

Date : 19/06/07

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Leak to cabin air. Data incorrect.
O₃	None
NO_x	None
TDLAS	None

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 295

Date: 19/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:13:12	Motor	Failed														Start P1 from takeoff	
11:15:00			7	10	1											FL010	
11:15:59				5	2											FL020	
11:17:02				3	2											FL030	
11:17:52				5	1											FL040	
11:19:00			8	20	5											FL050	
11:19:56				20	10											FL060	
11:21:00			9	30	10											FL070	
11:21:56				40	5											FL080	
11:22:59			10	20	2											FL090	
11:23:59				20	1											FL100	
11:24:59				20	5											FL110	
11:25:59			11	20	10											FL120	
11:26:58				50	5											FL130	
11:27:55				60	10											FL140	
11:28:55				90	10											FL150	
11:29:51			12	80	10											FL160	
11:30:47				50	10											FL170	
11:31:40			13	10	5											FL180	
11:32:34				20	5	5	800								9	FL190	
11:33:39				10	10	5	800								9	FL200	
11:34:46			33	2000	1000	1	800								9	FL210	
11:35:51			68	2	Noise											FL220	
11:37:05				1	Noise											FL230	
11:38:41				1	Noise											FL240	
11:39:41				1	Noise											End of P1 & Start Run 1.1 @ FL250	
11:40:00				1	Noise												
11:45:00				1	Noise												
11:50:00				1	1												
11:55:00				1	1												
12:00:00				1	1												
12:01:50																End of Run 1.1 & Start P2 from FL250	
12:03:15					1											FL240	
12:04:22				1	1											FL230	
12:05:40			69	1	Noise											FL220	
12:06:40				1	1											FL210	
12:07:50				1	1											FL200	
12:09:16				1	1											FL190	
12:10:54				1	1											FL180	
12:12:29				2	1											FL170	
12:14:08				10	10											FL160	
12:15:43				100	10											End of P2 & Start Run 2.1 @ FL150	
12:16:00				100	10												
12:18:00			70	100	10											Increased FFSSP signal level	
12:20:00			71	90	10												
12:22:00			72	90	10												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 295

Date: 19/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:24:00			74	80	10												
12:26:00			75	90	10												
12:28:00			77	80	10												
12:30:00			79	60	10												
12:32:00			80	50	10												
12:34:00			82	70	10												
12:35:49																End of Run 2.1 & Start P3	
12:37:20			84	90	10											FL160	
12:38:36			85	50	10											FL170	
12:39:50				10	10											FL180	
12:40:55			86	2	Noise											FL190	
12:42:12				1	Noise											FL200	
12:43:20				1	Noise											FL210	
12:44:23				1	Noise											FL220	
12:45:34				1	Noise											FL230	
12:46:47				1	Noise											FL240	
12:47:50				1	Noise											End of P3 & Start Run 3.1 @ FL250	
12:50:00				1	1												
12:55:00				1	1												
13:00:00				2	5												
13:05:00				2	Noise												
13:10:00				2	Noise												
13:15:00				1	Noise												
13:20:00				1	Noise												
13:25:00			87	3	Noise												
13:30:00				3	Noise												
13:35:00				2	Noise												
13:40:00				3	Noise												
13:45:00				3	1												
13:50:00				3	5												
13:57:58																End of Run 3.1 & Start P4 from FL250	
13:59:38				3	1											FL240	
14:00:45				2	1											FL230	
14:01:50				1	1											FL220	
14:02:59				1	1											FL210	
14:04:11				1	1											FL200	
14:05:26				1	1											FL190	
14:06:28				1	1											FL180	
14:07:40			88	100	10											FL170	
14:08:40			89	100	10											FL160	
14:09:46				90	10											FL150	
14:10:55				90	10											FL140	
14:12:04			90	100	10											FL130	
14:13:13			92	90	10											FL120	
14:14:58			93	100	10											FL110	
14:15:38				100	19											FL100	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 295

Date: 19/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:16:49			94	100	20											FL090	
14:17:52			95	100	20											FL080	
14:19:04			96	100	30											FL070	
14:20:05			97	100	20											FL060	
14:21:14			99	90	20											FL050	
14:22:18			100	90	10											FL040	
14:23:48																End of P4 & Start Run 4.1 @ 1000' ASL	
14:24:00			102	80	10												
14:26:00			104	90	20												
14:28:00			106	90	10												
14:30:00			109	100	30												
14:32:00			112	150	60												
14:34:00			116	200	60												
14:36:00			119	150	50												
14:38:00			123	120	50												
14:40:00			126	100	50												
14:42:00			128	100	30												
14:44:00			130	100	30												
14:45:10																End of Run 4.1	
14:46:57																Start Run 5.1 @ 1000 'ASL	
14:47:00			133	100	10												
14:49:00			135	100	10												
14:52:07																End of Run 5.1	
14:52:15																Start Orbits	
14:58:43																End Orbits	
15:00:32																Start P5 from 1000' ASL	
15:01:20			148	100	20											FL030	
15:02:17			149	100	20											FL040	
15:03:10			151	100	20											FL050	
15:03:50				100	20											FL060	
15:06:54																End of P5 & Start Run 6.1 @ FL075	
15:08:00			155	100	10												
15:10:00			157	100	10												
15:12:00			158	100	10												
15:14:00			160	100	20												
15:16:00			163	100	10												
15:16:58																End of Run 6.1 & Start P6 from FL075	
15:18:22			165	120	10											FL090	
15:19:11			166	90	8											FL100	
15:20:10				80	7											FL110	
15:21:03																End of P6 & Start Run 7.1 @ FL120	
15:22:00			167	80	10												
15:24:00			168	80	8												
15:26:00				80	8												
15:28:00			169	90	10												
15:30:00			170	90	10												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 295

Date: 19/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
15:31:03																End of Run 7.1 & Start P7	
15:32:10			171	90	10											FL130	
15:33:02			172	90	10											FL140	
15:33:59				100	10											FL150	
15:34:46			173	80	10											FL160	
15:35:36				10	1											FL170	
15:36:18																End of P7 & Start P8 from FL180	
15:37:25				10	5											FL170	
15:38:20			173	100	10											FL160	
15:39:08				100	10											FL150	
15:40:03			174	90	10											FL140	
15:40:50				80	10											FL130	
15:41:40				90	10											FL120	
15:42:33				90	10											FL110	
15:43:21				110	20											FL100	
15:44:09			175	110	30											FL090	
15:44:59				100	20											FL080	
15:45:45				80	10											FL070	
15:46:39			176	80	10											FL060	
15:48:11				80	8											FL050	
15:49:35			177	70	8											FL040	
15:52:49				40	2											FL030	
																End of Profile on Landing	
PCASP1 Motor failed Some noise on SID2 PCASP2 Flowrate = 1.0 CC/sec Changes in FFSSP signal offsets made during flight																	

B295_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:55:48.69 --- - - - -
09:55:48.69 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:55:48.69 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR /
                                Comment +++
09:55:48.69 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B295
09:55:48.69 --- - - - -
09:56:01.88 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:56:07.50 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:56:10.38 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:57:16.09 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:57:22.25 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:57:22.26 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:57:22.27 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:57:35.07 SWS - - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
09:57:38.80 SWS - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:57:43.16 USH - - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
09:57:46.51 USH - - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
09:57:48.64 USH - - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:57:53.16 LSH - - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:57:57.10 LSH - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:58:02.34 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:02.34 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:02.40 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:08.19 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:10.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:10.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:46.40 SWS - - - - Idling
09:58:48.25 USH - - - - Idling
09:58:50.14 LSH - - - - Idling
09:58:59.59 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:59:01.90 USH - - - - Idling
10:38:42.14 USH - - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
10:38:45.29 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:39:31.45 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
10:39:36.46 SWS - - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
10:39:39.26 SWS - - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:39:43.31 SWS - - - - Idling
10:39:47.02 SWS - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:39:55.42 SWS - - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:39:56.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:04:26.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:04:26.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:04:26.84 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:05:07.18 SWS - - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
11:05:10.61 SWS - - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
11:05:15.22 LSH - - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
11:05:26.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:05:26.19 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:05:26.19 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:05:30.80 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:05:31.99 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:05:34.12 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:05:34.72 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:05:42.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:05:47.46 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:05:48.11 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:05:51.93 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:05:55.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:05:56.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:06:01.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:06:01.84 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:06:01.92 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:06:06.23 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:06:07.63 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:06:09.94 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:07:12.13 --- - - - - *** Gerbil flight B295 Nouakchott to Niamey.
11:07:21.56 --- - - - - *** sws to 0deg
11:09:44.31 --- - - - - *** pirouette turn now
11:11:52.53 --- - - - - *** end pirouette now
11:12:52.66 --- - - - - *** sws to 90 aft for take off
11:14:01.10 --- - - - - *** sws to 7 f for profile climb
11:14:11.24 SWS - - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:14:16.48 SWS - - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
11:14:24.43 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:14:27.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

11:16:23.00	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
11:16:25.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:16:32.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:19.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 10F during climb
11:31:58.32	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
11:32:01.28	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
11:32:04.80	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
11:32:08.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:16.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:49.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** ac cloudpassing under
11:35:55.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** AC cloud layer between FL190 and FL218
11:36:13.69	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
11:36:22.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:36:30.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:16.92	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
11:38:21.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:29.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:39:54.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** start run at fl250 end profile
11:40:17.47	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
11:40:22.00	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
11:40:27.56	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
11:40:31.76	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 75ms.
11:40:35.91	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
11:40:39.28	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
11:40:42.25	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:40:46.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:47.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:40:51.11	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
11:40:53.73	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:40:55.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:40:59.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:56.66	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 75ms.
11:49:59.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:01.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:06.44	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
11:50:11.14	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
11:50:15.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:23.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:33.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** currently flying over cloud
11:56:07.32	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:56:09.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:56:17.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:05.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r1.1 start P2 to FL190
12:07:59.81	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
12:08:08.87	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
12:08:13.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:21.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:24.89	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
12:08:28.16	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
12:08:29.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:32.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:07.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** still profiling but now to FL150
12:16:08.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profil 2 start r2.1 at FL150
12:16:20.77	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
12:16:25.41	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
12:16:27.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:16:35.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:35.29	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
12:27:38.66	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
12:27:41.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:41.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:41.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:44.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:45.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:50.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:36:01.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r2.1 start P3
12:43:20.97	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
12:43:24.87	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
12:43:27.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:43:35.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:48:10.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P3 start r3.1 at FL250
12:48:31.82	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
12:48:36.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:48:44.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:07.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:08.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:06:08.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:06:10.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:12.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:06:16.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:49.00	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
13:13:51.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:00.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:01.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:12.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws still at 174R
13:39:34.60	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
13:39:37.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:39:45.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:39:58.75	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
13:40:01.85	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
13:40:04.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:06.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:09.72	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
13:40:13.61	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
13:40:15.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:20.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:44:34.57	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 75ms.
13:44:38.17	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
13:44:42.78	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
13:44:46.27	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
13:44:51.63	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
13:44:57.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:44:57.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:44:57.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:45:00.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:01.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:05.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:34.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** ever thick dust at the moment. Surface not easily visible
14:00:17.75	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:00:24.02	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 250ms.
14:00:28.92	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
14:00:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:01:00.82	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
14:01:08.71	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
14:01:13.34	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
14:01:17.64	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
14:01:20.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:20.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:21.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:01:25.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:28.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:28.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:35.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
14:07:53.24	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
14:07:56.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:04.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:10.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** In dust at FL160
14:11:41.34	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
14:11:44.92	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:11:48.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:53.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:13.59	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
14:19:16.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:20.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:27.07	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:21:31.75	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
14:21:34.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:37.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:58.63	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
14:22:08.14	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
14:22:10.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:18.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:10.34	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 150ms.
14:24:17.24	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:24:21.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:21.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:22.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:25.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:26.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:29.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:35.73	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:25:09.26	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:25:14.29	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.

14:25:17.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:25:21.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:42.25	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
14:26:45.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:48.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:33:24.96	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:35:22.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:22.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:23.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:26.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:27.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:30.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:43.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** low level runu at MPA
14:36:14.95	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:38:11.38	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
14:38:16.71	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
14:38:19.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:24.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:43:13.29	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:43:22.51	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
14:43:26.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:43:29.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:38.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 2000ft
14:45:18.69	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:45:29.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** positioning for orbits
14:45:33.86	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:45:38.35	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
14:45:42.25	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 75ms.
14:45:53.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:55.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:57.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:57.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:57.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:58.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:02.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:05.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:05.40	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
14:47:10.64	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
14:47:13.39	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
14:47:26.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:29.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:32.61	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
14:48:34.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:48:37.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:06.90	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
14:52:10.77	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 30ms.
14:52:20.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 1
14:52:32.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:33.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:32.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end
14:53:45.88	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
14:53:49.50	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
14:53:53.36	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
14:53:55.80	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:53:59.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:59.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:59.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:54:00.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:02.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:04.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:06.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 2
14:55:17.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** end
14:55:29.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:29.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:29.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:30.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:33.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:34.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:38.29	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
14:55:41.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:41.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:41.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:55:42.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:45.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:55:47.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:05.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 3
14:56:17.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** start 180deg

```

14:57:30.74 --- - - - - *** end
14:57:39.72 --- - - - - *** start 4
14:58:54.63 --- - - - - *** end orbits
14:59:45.41 --- - - - - *** all orbits at 50 deg aob
15:02:48.85 SWS - - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 150ms.
15:02:53.93 SWS - - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 250ms.
15:02:59.09 SWS - - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
15:03:02.96 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:07.39 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:03:33.99 SWS - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:03:36.08 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:03:40.51 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:06:08.33 LSH - - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:06:11.29 LSH - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:06:14.76 USH - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
15:06:17.61 USH - - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:06:20.77 USH - - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:06:24.49 USH - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:06:30.87 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:06:31.02 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:06:31.52 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:06:35.31 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:06:39.02 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:06:39.45 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:07:11.04 --- - - - - *** start r5.1 at FL075
15:07:18.40 LSH - - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
15:07:20.85 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:07:28.78 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:17:10.63 --- - - - - *** end r5.1 start p6
15:17:28.75 USH - - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:17:44.30 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:17:49.74 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:21:41.65 --- - - - - *** end p6 startt r6.1 at FL120
15:28:39.37 SWS - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:28:42.42 SWS - - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 350ms.
15:28:47.22 SWS - - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
15:28:53.22 USH - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:28:58.71 USH - - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
15:29:02.29 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:29:02.31 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:29:02.82 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:29:10.24 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:29:10.45 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:29:10.76 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:32:40.21 USH - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:32:41.93 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:32:49.87 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:44:24.26 --- - - - - *** on descent to Niamey.
15:44:28.77 --- - - - - *** in dust
15:44:34.04 --- - - - - *** at 8000ft
15:44:56.35 SWS - - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
15:44:58.52 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:45:06.45 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:56:54.44 --- - - - - *** data stop

```

ARIES flight log

Flight: B295	page 1 of 4
Date: 19/Jun/2007 Operator(s): S. ROGERS	Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2
Loc./Notes: NOUAKCHOTT TO NIAMEY (GERBILS)	

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
10 08 35	ON THE PAN	1x60	CH	C	71	31	Script 2 (Cold 1x60; Hot 1x60)
10 16 15	"	"	CH				Script 1 Random script - hit wrong button
10 17 42	"	"	CH	C	71	33	Script 1
10 19	"	120x1	Z	O	71	32	
10 20 04	"	1x60	CH	C	71	33	Script 1 (shutter closing during C)
11 04 45	TAXIING	1x60	CH	O	71	36	
11 09	Pirouette	360x1	Z	O	71	37	Pirouette at start of run
11 11 57		1x60	CH	C			Script 1
11 15	TAKE OFF						Running CBS? Setting to 40°C
	PIF						Shutter open during profile to help cooling.
11 40	R1						↳ Closed at start of run/end of profile.
11 41 16	FL250	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1 - Aborted (operator stupidity)
11 42 31	"	"	CH	C	71	41	Script 2
11 43 44	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	8/8 cloud below Clouds quite brown! ↓
11 46 53	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 2
11 48 08	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	8/8 cloud below ↓
11 51 13	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1 ¹¹⁵⁷² Sonda
11 52 28	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	8/8 Dust! below (no cloud?) ↓
11 55 34	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
11 56 53	"	480x1	N	C	71	41	8/8 dust below surface barely visible ↓
12 00 56	P2 ↓	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
12 15 44	R2 FL150	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
12 16 59	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	Thick dust below, thinner above ↓
12 20 06	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 21 58	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below - a bit thinner. ↓
12 25 05	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 26 18	"	360x1	N	C	71	42	↓
12 29 28	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 30 40	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below a bit thinner ↓
12 33 50	"	1x60	CH	C	71	40	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13295

page 2 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12 47 52	^{FL250} FL250	1x60	CH	C	70	41	Script 1
12 49 06		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, not thick ↓
12 52 09		1x60	CH	C	71	42	Script 1
12 53 25		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, surface visible - later obscured. dust storm or cloud?
12 56 30		1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
12 57 44		360x1	N	C			Surface barely visible. ↓
13 00 45		1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
13 02 02		360x1	N	C	71	41	Cloud? & dust below ↓
13 05 06		1x60	CH	C	70	41	Script 1
13 06 20		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, thin-ish. Ciabone ↓
13 09 23		1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
13 10 38		360x1	N	C	71	41	↓
13 13 43		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 14 58		360x1	N	C	71	42	Dust below ↓
13 18 01		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 19 16		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, surface barely visible ↓
13 22 18		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 23 33		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below ↓
13 26 36		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 27 51		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below ↓
13 30 53		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 32 20		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust below, Cu to starboard. ↓
13 33 25		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 36 40		360x1	N	C	71	41	Increasing cloud below ↓
13 39 47		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 41 00		360x1	N	C	71	41	Cloud below (white!) ^{Breaking up later} leaving dust. ↓
13 44 08		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 45 20		360x1	N	C	71	40	Thick dust below, surface obscured. ↓
13 48 24		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 49 42		360x1	N	C	71	41	Thick dust ↓
13 52 43		1x60	CH	C	71	41	

Flight:

B295

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:44:39

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

26/06/2007 11:48:55

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B295

Date: 19 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 19 JUN 07

Flight No: 1395

Pre-Flighter:

Item	√ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	☐	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☐	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	☒	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	W/S
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU	Align	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☐	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	☐	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	☒	FWVS	Set up	
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	☐	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	☐	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☐	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	☒	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	☒	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	☒	CGPS	Set up	
28	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	☐			
	☐			
	☐			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	<i>winding broken - in 5/16/02</i>
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	☐	IOEX applied		
45	☐	Traps empty (weekly only)		

B295 Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

msg_new_dust_product_1015z.jpg

EAAO51 MSG dust product 19 Jun 2007 1015 UTC

seviri_1315z.jpg

EAAO41 MSG dust RGB 19 Jun 2007 1315 UTC

msg_new_dust_product_1315z.jpg

EAAO51 MSG dust product 19 Jun 2007 1315 UTC

seviri_1315z.jpg

EAAO41 MSG dust RGB 19 Jun 2007 1315 UTC

New plot, same times

Flight B295 12:35:15

Heading 91 deg Speed 274 knots Height 15.0kft Press 571mb

Lat 18°0.0'N Long 9°36.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/ 110 deg

Temp -1.76C Dewpoint -9.82C

From 11:21:30 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	45315	secs	⊙ AI
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	1166.17	W m-2	○
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	602.47	W m-2	○
---	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	409.14	W m-2	○
---	LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	198.43	W m-2	○

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B295:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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